

Dendrostream: Exploring Tree Stress and Climate Change Through Sonification and Visualisation

Tug F. O’Flaherty

240751898

Dr. Anna Xambó

Sound and Music Computing MSc.

Abstract—Tree growth and climate data is frequently presented in scientific manners, often uninterpretable without specialist knowledge. As the importance of highlighting climate change increases, and more laypeople are interested in understanding such data, alternative presentation methods should be explored. This work aims to discover suitable representation methods to aid non-experts’ analysis of climate and tree data, through differing modalities. Using a participatory design approach, five participants of differing backgrounds, assisted in the creation of a web-based sonification and visualisation tool, to display data received from an existing hardware tree-talker prototype. The tool was shown to increase some users’ perceived data knowledge, and identified benefits for customisable multimodal data presentation approaches in improving data interpretation. This initial exploration identifies that tailored sonification and visualisation presentation methods offer the potential to assist in tree and climate data communication to non-specialist audiences, to improve public understanding and engagement.

Index Terms—Sonification, Data Visualization, Music, Human Computer Interaction, Climate Change, Forests

I. INTRODUCTION

Climate change concerns prolonged environmental changes to rain, temperature, humidity, and pressure, culminating in weather abnormalities and irregularities (Abbass et al., 2022). With widespread, affecting agriculture, biodiversity, and forestry, rapid corrective measures are required (Santos et al., 2022). However, climate change existence is strongly supported by extensive scientific evidence, scientific denialists remain prevalent (Björnberg et al., 2017).

Presently, tree and climate data are frequently presented using scientific terms, hindering understandability by non-experts, public engagement, and lobbying for climate policy changes (Entradas et al., 2019). Such lobbying – where the public seeks to influence policymakers – is crucial. However, to achieve greater impact, dissemination of climate change information should be informed by scientists and data-based citizen science “learn-by-doing” projects (De Sherbinin et al., 2021).

However, climate and tree data, and the relation between trees and climate change, is lesser discussed than climate change, as such data is complex, technically-oriented, challenging to obtain, and less directly-perceivable. Nonetheless, tree monitoring data provides insights into tree health, which, when combined with data from the tree’s environmental surroundings, can facilitate individuals in better connecting with the landscape, highlighting tree stress increases due to extreme climatic events, and accordingly, caring for the planet.

Two common approaches to data presentation are sonification – presenting data points through mapping to non-speech audio parameters – and visualisation – presenting data through visual imagery. Although visualisation techniques, including graphs, are widespread, sonification has been proposed as a promising method to effectively communicate complex scientific data to the public, assuming that the audio design with respect to the data – referred to as mapping – has strongly been considered (Sawe et al., 2020). Further suggested benefits of sonification include analysis, data accessibility, and artistic expression (Hermann et al., 2011; Kramer et al., 2010). Moreover, public understanding of climate change may be increased through presentation in accessible visualisation forms (Newell et al., 2016), in turn, also assisting in policymaking (Daron et al., 2015).

This research aims to answer the question: *Can sonification and visualisation approaches be applied to tree and climate data, for the purpose of democratisation, to raise public awareness of tree data and climate change?* To address this, three research questions (RQs), covering differing aspects of the investigation, are proposed:

- *RQ1: To what extent do sonification and visualisation approaches, applied to climate and tree data, affect public opinion and knowledge of such data, and climate change?*
- *RQ2: To what degree are customisable or varied presentation modes beneficial in raising awareness of tree data and climate change, and prompting changing future plans?*
- *RQ3: Which sonification and visualisation data parameter mappings provide the greatest engagement with the general public?*

This project aims to present scientific tree and climate data in an interpretable and analysable manner, through the creation of a tool utilising sonification and visualisation, with the aim of highlighting tree stress, the impact trees are caused by climate change, and democratising science. Democratisation benefits increased public understanding and engagement, and a greater trust of scientific information, with non-scientists better aligning with scientific findings, strengthening such scientific views, and reducing the likelihoods of scientific denial (Green Deal Projects Support Office, 2024).

Varied presentation approaches of sonification and visualisation are required to meet varying demographics, benefitting

engagement and raising awareness (Enge et al., 2024).

This paper presents the design and development of a web-based software tool for sonifying and visualising tree and climate data, received from a previously developed hardware prototype device¹. This work builds upon initial proposals to sonify the device data, using drone and frequency modulation (FM) synthesiser parameter mappings (O’Flaherty et al., 2025), developing further musical sonifications, with a greater focus on visualisation approaches and usability. The participatory design approach followed is discussed, alongside the implemented tool’s sonic and visual parameter mappings and outputs, and the results obtained through an extensive evaluative user study.

II. RELATED WORK

This section presents previous work in sonification, visualisation, and multimodal presentation, used to present tree and climate data.

A. Sonification

A number of existing approaches have sought to utilise sonification methods to present tree-related data, including the DIY real-time sonification of soil moisture data using Bela and Supercollider, with the data using a one-to-many parameter mapping, focussing on rhythm and slowly-evolving soundscapes to bring usually unknown soil moisture changes into public view (Suchánek, 2020). Similarly, the sonification of compost temperature has been conducted, utilising a one-to-one parameter mapping from the rescaled temperature output to the frequency of an oscillator, in Max/MSP, highlighting the process of biological decomposition (Parker, 2015). However, in both cases, the principle concern was artistic expression, arguably with a more limited focus on the scientific accuracy of the data presentation.

In contrast, sound installations have been created to spatially sonify climate change data, conveying climate trends to relative success. Using a combination of one-to-many and many-to-many parameter mappings, temperature change, CO₂, ice sheet mass, and sea level variation were mapped to the playback of natural sounds, including rain, wind, and birds, alongside percussion and drones (Zelada and Çamcı, 2023). Results showed that most participants correctly identified data trends, and believed the sonification to accurately represent the data. Generally, listeners noted that the use of spatial audio was beneficial to the overall soundscape, and identification of each data variable.

Past work has also seen the creation of natural soundscapes, for the purpose of highlighting forests and their canopy, through ambisonic playback of highpass-filtered forest field recordings, to present a subtle representation of such spaces within urban settings (López, 2014). Moreover, non-linear approaches to sonification of air temperature have been proposed, allowing users to query a given data collection, and hear the corresponding melody of the air temperature from that year

(Kalonaris, 2022), benefitting targeted understanding larger datasets.

Sonification has been used for the purpose of public engagement with urban air pollution data, and was shown to have succeeded in raising public awareness of these climate issues (St Pierre and Droumeva, 2016; Terboven et al., 2023), thus highlighting the potential for sonification as a promising means of data dissemination to non-scientists. Further uses of sonification relate to citizen science projects, including the sonification of water temperature and hydrophonic sounds received from a kayak, with results showing increased data understanding and engagement levels (Griffiths et al., 2017).

B. Visualisation

Visualisation encompasses numerous forms of visual data presentation, including the widespread form of graphs and charts. Bar and line are crucial to climate change data presentation, although they should present a clear message, use clear and distinguishing colours, and be easily interpretable while visually appealing (Painter et al., 2021). Moreover, preferences are often made for visualisations with more detail, allowing users to obtain a greater understanding of the presented data, with considerations being made to aesthetics and chart familiarity (Daron et al., 2015). However, abstraction is noted as being beneficial to improve generalisability of visualisations, alongside appropriate visual complexity and patterns, to aid interpretation, and clear examples, to contextualise the data being displayed (Wang et al., 2020).

Moreover, cartographic methods of visualisation have been developed, conveying sap flow and dendrometer sensor data from their respective trees, to produce radial maps containing the tree’s data from virtual satellite views, although a user study into its effectiveness is currently being conducted (Chew et al., 2024). Alternative visualisation proposals include the use of dynamic, interactive representations of climate change data, through the creation of abstract animations depicting landscapes, which update their labelled elements based on the received data values (Newell et al., 2016). When compared to static line graph visualisations, findings suggests the strengths of static visualisations for users wishing to obtain a detailed understanding of the data, whereas the abstract visualisations improved audience engagement and interest (Newell et al., 2016), suggesting the importance of different forms of visualisation to increase data accessibility.

C. Multimodal Sonification and Visualisation

Many multimodal sonification and visualisation tools have been produced, pairing sonification with visualisation techniques, to present data. One such web application, to explore environmental sounds and understand the impacts of climate change, is ClimaSynth (Panourgia et al., 2024), intended to improve data accessibility through pairing granular-synthesised sonification of real audio recordings, with an interactive cluster-based interface. Each canvas area is mapped directly to a data point, adjusting the attack, decay, density, delay, feedback, and pitch parameters of the corresponding granular

¹<http://bit.ly/4mQKCDZ>

synthesis sound. However, such approach is limited, as it presents only nature-based sounds, shown to be disengaging with audiences (Worrall, 2019), with limited visualisations and no display of the corresponding data values being currently presented.

In contrast, a Max 8-based (Cycling '74, 2025) weather data system, WeatherChimes, presents line graph and abstract visualisations of collected temperature and rainfall data, with musical sonifications for each data variable, varying the played tracks, and thus overall emotional state, of the sonification, based on the data readings received (Woo et al., 2023), however with limited user personalisation.

An installation, Trees, presented a time-lapse video a tree in its environment, alongside graphical representations of the climate measurements, alongside simple ambisonic sonification, with data variables typically mapped to the amplitude of sounds with distinct timbres (Maeder and Zweifel, 2016). Although relatively simplistic, the project gained widespread media success. A further installation, a conversation between trees, presented contemporary art-based visualisations with corresponding tree and climate data values, for user interaction via a smartphone app, and spoken-word artist discussion of their journey through the forest (Jacobs et al., 2013). It was noted that visitor feedback and appeal was mixed, due to the contemporary approach undertaken (Jacobs et al., 2013), and the lack of numerical visualisations and sonifications may have reduced data analysis and accessibility.

Building upon the identified strengths and pitfalls in past visualisations and sonifications for tree stress and climate data, this research explores new, interactive forms of presentation, for the benefit of data accessibility and interpretation by non-scientists. Through integrating prior work, it is intended that the developed tool addresses past shortcomings, to improve data democratisation.

III. METHODOLOGY

To develop the proposed sonification and visualisation tool, a participatory design user study was conducted, to ensure user views were consistently considered throughout the creation process (Wacnik et al., 2025). 5 participants were recruited, using the NIME Community mailing list, to benefit participants' musical interest. Participants were selected for diversity, to ensure a broad range of viewpoints were considered, thus increasing the potential generalisability of the system for a wider audience. Participation involved the completion of an initial pre-survey, subsequent background interview, features and design evaluation survey, developed tool evaluation interview, and post-survey.

A. Requirements Analysis

Participants first completed a background experience survey, to obtain a clear understanding of their disciplines. All participants had experience with music, science, and forestry, although not all were familiar in statistics. Participants were asked for their views on perceived usefulness of different sonification and visualisation presentation approaches, based on

the forms identified in the related work, including graphs, abstract graphics, and sonification musicality, in addition to data presentation across multiple modalities. Participant responses were collated, and the sum of responses of 'useful' and 'very useful' were used to identify the proposed sonification and visualisation presentation approaches, to be implemented. Results showed a preference for sonification and visualisation being presented together, with charts and graphs, detailed graphics, and semi-musical sonifications, being preferred.

Participants were also asked for their prior expectations of the study, in an attempt to ensure the developed tool, met their expectations. All participants stated an interest for understanding more about sonification techniques to explore tree, environmental, and climate change data.

Further to this, a semi-structured introductory individual interview was held with each participant, to gain further insights into views on the sonification and visualisation methods they believe would be beneficial, and features they expected to be present within the tool. Both survey and interview responses were combined to develop a features list, used to encourage design thinking (Norman, 2013), subsequently validated with participants, through a further survey. This sought to ensure the feature accuracy, and identify any missing features, prior to development (Wacnik et al., 2025). Participants could express their opinions on each other's anonymous ideas, preventing the over-fitting of the system's requirements to any one such participant. Received feedback was positive, with most users agreeing with the proposed functionality, and indicating some additional missing features, including volume mixing of sonification streams, and abstract visuals, although users did not believe any of the proposed features were unnecessary.

B. Design

The features list and participant interview responses, directly informed the tool's design. During an interview, a participant acknowledged their desire for the system to use a dashboard layout, containing large buttons with associated iconography and textual descriptions, thus this formed the basis of the user interface design. Notably, two participants stated during interviews that the system should provide minimal visible controls, with further controls only displayed when additional customisation is desired, to minimise potential confusion or overwhelming of users. Such ideas led to the visible panel-based design, present within the visualisation modes, enabling users to view or hide the additional panel controls, as necessary. These design ideas, with consideration with respect to developing a clear conceptual model, and the function controls utilising appropriate affordances and signifiers (Norman, 2013), were formalised within the creation of initial low-fidelity hand-sketched wireframes. These wireframes were subsequently refined, with added additional detail, to produce clear, medium-fidelity digital wireframes, with all included functionality from the features list.

To avoid overwhelming participants, thus reducing involvement (Jäckel et al., 2023), both the features list and medium-fidelity wireframes formed the second survey, completed by

the study participants. Participant feedback was positive, with most stating that the design appeared clear and intuitive, with one unsure of the line graph visualisation axes scales used. Notably, one participant suggested changing the hamburger icon to a directional arrows, used on the options panel toggle button, as a clearer signifier (Norman, 2013), with another stating additional accessibility requirements, such as graph plot colour controls, would be beneficial. All users responded that there were no superfluous existing controls. These design suggestions were subsequently incorporated into the implemented version of the tool.

C. Implementation

The following section examines the implementation process of the *Dendrostream* sonification and visualisation tool, including the frontend website, and backend application programming interface (API). The importance of the tool's accessibility, to benefit data democratisation, led to the decision to implement the system as a website (Green Deal Projects Support Office, 2024). This provides users with free, remote access without specialised hardware, unlike location-based installation practices, such as Jacobs et al. (2013), or the use of costly proprietary software, such as Woo et al. (2023).

1) *Frontend*: The *Dendrostream* frontend web application² was developed using React (Meta Platforms, Inc., 2025), a frontend web application library, chosen due to its element-level page re-rendering, improving performance and reducing network requests, benefitting accessibility on low-performance devices (Gackenheimer, 2015). The React Router DOM library was used to provide page routing based on the entered URL, to prevent the standard page re-rendering process usually required upon URL changes (Remix Software, Inc., 2025). All sonifications were implemented using the Web Audio API, a browser-based audio library designed to facilitate the sound synthesis, playback, offering the lowest-level control of browser audio in real-time, with minimal latency (Chetwynd et al., 2021). Audio performance was strongly considered, due to the necessity of sonification playback aligning with the visualisation of the corresponding data point.

Graphical visualisations, namely bar charts and line graphs, were implemented using the d3.js JavaScript library, enabling the creation of powerful graphs, through low-level control of the individual graphical elements, including tooltips, axes, and plot points (Bostock, 2025). Similarly, p5.js, a JavaScript-based implementation of the creative coding Processing language (The p5.js Team, 2025), was used to produce the dials dashboard, and forest scene interactive animation visualisations. Such language offers significant flexibility over the produced visuals, with default functions to draw visual elements including text and shapes, and re-render animations based on data or window size changes. Bootstrap, alongside custom CSS styling, was used to reduce the time required to implement a user-friendly interface design (The Bootstrap

Team, 2025), thus permitting more consideration to be made to the creation of the sonifications and visualisations.

The requested tree-talker tree and climate data records are received as a JavaScript Object Notation (JSON) object array, via the in-built JavaScript `fetch()` command, from the accompanying backend API. Moreover, the socket.io client application is used to create and manage web socket connections with the backend (Socket.IO Team, 2025), to obtain real-time data updates, upon a new the tree-talker reading becoming available. The developed frontend application was subsequently deployed, to facilitate public access for study participants, using Cloudflare Pages, due to its low cost, and support for Node.js (Cloudflare, Inc., 2025; Node.js Foundation, 2025), required to run the built React application.

The tool implements four core sonifications and visualisations: Primary Data, Derived Data, Personalised Data, and Custom Audio. All sonifications variables are able to be muted and volume-adjusted through the use of the Web Audio API `Gain` node, with visualisation variables able to be hidden. Moreover, the global sonification or visualisation may be enabled or hidden, and the data source, playback speed, graph zoom, and master volume, controlled, to benefit data interpretation. The tool provides detailed help guides, sonification and visualisation mapping and analysis information, and the corresponding dataset's tree information, to promote engagement, and benefit interpretability and accessibility. Upon starting playback, a 632.46 Hz reference tone plays for 0.5 seconds, calculated as the perceptual midpoint frequency between the highest and lowest sonification frequencies (Müller, 2015), to contextualise the upcoming sonification values, a limitation noted by Worrall (2019).

Fig. 1. Dendrostream tool's Derived Data Preset 1 function, displaying a line graph, with accompanying drone sonification

Primary Data provides five presets, each presenting an increasingly more creative sonification and visualisation approach. Preset 1 offers a line graph visualisation of the four sensor data variables received from the tree-talker device: displacement (tree trunk expansion), soil moisture, temperature, and humidity. Each value is plotted with a separate line on the same graph, with an X-axis scale from 0 to 100, to benefit the identification of variable interplay, as shown in Figure 1. As the displacement reading is typically lower than 1, this is rescaled by a factor of 100, to align more clearly with the other values received from the sensors. The

²Deployment: <https://stf-sv-tool.pages.dev>, Codebase: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16917317>

accompanying drone-based sonification remaps the expected variable value range to a frequency range of 200 Hz to 2000 Hz, to ensure the generated tone is more listenable, and audible on all audio devices (Hermann et al., 2011). This rescaled frequency is applied to the corresponding variable's `OscillatorNode` frequency, using a one-to-one mapping, with variable `OscillatorNode` using differing timbres, produced through varying the carrier waveform type, to benefit interpretation. All variables are placed in distinct spatial locations, through the use of the `PannerNode`, to benefit interpretation (Worrall, 2019).

Similarly, Preset 2 offers identical presentations, but with the expanded capability of presenting two datasets, promoting comparison between trees and their respective climates. The first dataset is presented in a line graph above the second dataset, and its sonification is played through the left channel, while the second dataset is played through the right channel, using the `StereoPannerNode`, permitting audible comparison.

Preset 3 provides an averaged bar chart visualisation, presenting groups of a user-selectable time-windowed, averaged data variable reading, for each averaging bin. This is accompanied by a Frequency Modulation (FM) synthesiser sonification, with one synthesiser produced for each variable, with the respective variable's rescaled frequency being used as the synthesiser's carrier frequency (Hermann et al., 2011). All synthesisers' modulator frequency is mapped to the rescaled soil moisture reading, harmonicity to the displacement, and modulation index to the rescaled humidity reading, applying a one-to-many mapping approach to aid in the detection of the subtle changes in these value readings (Hermann et al., 2011).

Preset 4 presents a data dial dashboard visualisation, containing the current data value, and a coloured ring representing its magnitude with respect to its expected minimum and maximum value. Each variable reading is mapped to the closest musical note corresponding to its value within the current musical scale (either Dorian, Aeolian, or Major), with the displacement mapped to a piano sound, soil moisture to a plucked guitar, temperature to a smooth lead synthesiser, and humidity to a flute, created through setting the appropriate envelope, through manipulating the current value of a `GainNode`, and using `OscillatorNodes` with appropriate partials and waveform types, tremolo (produced using a combination of an `OscillatorNode` and `GainNode` for the flute, and vibrato (similarly produced) for the smooth lead synthesiser (Reiss, 2022). Each variable sonification is set to play randomly, with the soundscape evolving every 3 seconds, and changing scale every 5 minutes, to produce a pleasant background soundscape for prolonged listening of live data (Worrall, 2019).

Preset 5 offers an animated visualisation depicting a tree within a forest landscape, with the sensor reading's displacement value mapped to the tree size, depicting the tree trunk expansion, soil moisture to the soil colour (and cracks, if the soil is dry), temperature to the sun colour and size, and sky colour, and humidity to the cloud size and number, reflecting real-life changes. A musical sonification is presented, with dis-

placement mapped to a piano playing a melody, soil moisture to a bass guitar playing a bassline, temperature to a piano playing chords, and humidity mapped to an electric guitar, emulated using the techniques outlined in Preset 4 (Hermann et al., 2011).

Derived Data contains identical mapping approaches to those outlined in the Primary Data function, although with calculated inference values for tree stress, through the addition of the vapour pressure deficit (VPD) on all presets, except Preset 3, which presents the tree mean growth, highlighting the daily average growth of the tree. Moreover, the VPD is mapped to the sonification musical scale type, changing the musical scale to Major if the VPD is in range, thus the tree is not stressed (Sanginés de Cárcer et al., 2018), reflecting the listening experience (Hermann et al., 2011). In Preset 5, the VPD is mapped to drum hit frequency and when the tree is not stressed, playback of ambient sounds, including birdsong and crickets. Within the visualisation, it is mapped to a happy face when the tree is unstressed, and a sad face, when the tree is stressed, indicating the tree's current condition.

Fig. 2. Dendrostream tool's Personalised Data function, presenting forest scene animation visuals and musical sonification

The Personalised Data function provides all sonification and visualisation methods used within the Derived Data presets, although permitting the user to customise the sonification instrument and spatial audio panning used to represent each variable, as shown in Figure 2. The visualisation type used, and further visualisation settings, including colour palette and grid background, may also be selected, providing greater flexibility than the pre-defined mappings.

Fig. 3. Dendrostream tool's Custom Audio function, displaying key signature options for the piece, and pitch configuration options for each instrument presented within the sonification

Custom Audio presents an alternative approach to sonification, with a user journey comprising input sliders and drop-down menus, to generate personalised sonifications, through the same sonification options offered within the Personalised Data function, as shown in Figure 3. However, full audio parameter controls are provided, including synthesis modulation index, modulator frequency and waveform type, instrument playing styles and frequency ranges, and the addition of effects, including equalisation (EQ), compression, distortion, delay, reverb, and tremolo, to improve data accessibility through creative possibilities (Hermann et al., 2011).

Source Data offers documentation on the usage of the backend API, including its available endpoints, returned JSON object array, and raw JSON file data downloads, with additional troubleshooting steps, enabling the creation and exploration of the data beyond the sonification and visualisation approaches presented within the tool, for increased accessibility.

2) *Backend API*: A backend API³ was implemented using Express.js, an efficient representational state transfer (REST) API framework, facilitating the handling of client requests, necessary processing, and subsequent response (Express.js Team, 2025). The API serves to provide a requesting client, either the frontend *Dendrostream* web application, or a user's Source Data requesting application such as Max/MSP (Cycling '74, 2025), the respective tree-talker device's sensor readings, based on the requested endpoint. Data is returned as a standard JSON object array, containing one object per 30 minute sensor recording, with properties for the record timestamp, displacement, soil moisture, temperature, and humidity readings, facilitating interoperability with most network-enabled software and web applications.

Upon receiving a data HTTP GET request, the appropriate handler uses a JavaScript `fetch()` command, to request the data from the associated tree-talker device's API, before returning the data, in a cleansed format, to the client. If such device request is unsuccessful, the API returns the associated device's locally-stored historical dataset, to provide the client with a source of data to present. Device endpoints are sequentially numbered and return the latest device record, when using the `?latest=true` URL query string parameter. Moreover, the API provides web socket connection, using the `socket.io` library, to the frontend application, polling device endpoints every 10 minutes to obtain data changes, and transmitting new data records to active client sockets, allowing them to present the latest data records in near real-time.

The backend also implements Nodemailer, a JavaScript email transmission client (Nodemailer Team, 2025), to send email messages to a system administration email account. When an HTTP POST request, used to securely transmit data within the request body, is received at the corresponding Contact Form API endpoint, Nodemailer sends an email containing the information message, informing the administration team of a user query to answer. Furthermore, Nodemailer

emails automated alert messages when a tree-talker device has stopped streaming for over 5 hours, indicating a potential device problem causing data loss, or when a displacement sensor reading value is greater than $10\mu\text{m}$, indicating an it is out of normal range, and requires manual recalibration. Alerts are only sent once per 24 hour period, to prevent unnecessary message transmission, but seek to benefit remote tree-talker device management.

The backend API uses the Dotenv JavaScript library, facilitating the reading of environment variables throughout the application, to ensure sensitive data, including email account credentials, are abstracted from the main codebase (Motdotla, 2025). The API is deployed using Render, a low-cost Node.js (Node.js Foundation, 2025) hosting service, designed for effective management of backend APIs, permitting its online access (Render, Inc., 2025).

D. Evaluation

Following the tool's implementation, white-box testing was performed, to ensure the system's functioned as expected, and identify any potential bugs (Nidhra and Dondeti, 2012), prior to participant evaluation using a technology probes approach, to better understand user needs and experiences (Hutchinson et al., 2003).

Following the rectification of known issues, study participants were invited to use the tool for a period of one week, prior to partaking in a semi-structured individual interview, to provide their views on the tool and its sonifications and visualisations. Participants subsequently completed a post-survey, to discover their subsequent knowledge of climate change and tree data, and any future plans.

Concurrently, a second evaluation study was conducted, for the purpose of validating the generalisability and suitability of the developed tool for a wider group of users (Wacnik et al., 2025). A separate group of participants were recruited via calls to mailing lists of varied disciplines, including Environmental Humanities, Music and Science, and CHIME. Similarly, participants used the developed tool, prior to completing a survey outlining their background, knowledge of tree and climate data, opinions on the tool, and future plans.

IV. RESULTS

A. Full Study

The full study was undertaken by 5 participants across Europe, North America, and Oceania, with an age range of between 20 and 69. One participant identifies as female, three participants identify as male, and one participant identifies as genderqueer. All participants reported having prior experience of music and science, with most having experience of statistics, and some of forestry.

1) *RQ1: Knowledge of Trees and Climate Change*: With respect to the extent sonification and visualisation approaches can affect public climate and tree data understanding, following usage of the tool, 40% of participants believed that their knowledge and opinion on climate change and tree

³Deployment: <https://stf-sv-tool-api.onrender.com>, Codebase: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16917345>

data increased, with the remaining 60% believing it to have remained the same.

Moreover, after interacting with the data, 80% of participants reported that they might have been able to perceive tree stress and the effects of environmental conditions on the tree's growth rate after using the tool, with 20% of participants believing they did not.

2) *RQ2: Customisable and Varied Data Presentation Modes*: 80% of participants stated that this study has inspired them to do something new in the future, while 20% of participants believe it may inspire them to do something new, with one participant stating that they wish to further their environmental engagement through technology, with more sustainable practices. However, a different participant believed there was too much personalisation available, and would rather be presented with more refined presets, and fewer options.

3) *RQ3: Sonification and Visualisation Mappings*: When asked regarding their most favoured and disliked sonification preferences, four participants enjoyed both the Custom Audio and animation presentations, with three participants benefitting from the Personalised Data functionality. Two participants stated that they considered the bar chart to be useful, while two participants enjoyed the drone sonification. One participant valued the FM synthesis sonification, with one participant appreciating the line graph visualisation. One participant stated that they appreciated the project's intentions, but they believed the data presentations did not work, and the sounds were 'too harsh'.

B. Evaluation Study

The evaluation study was undertaken by 3 participants based in the United Kingdom, with an age range of between 20 and 39. Two participants identify as female, and one participant identifies as male. Two participants reported having prior experience of music, forestry, and statistics, and all stated that they have experience of science.

1) *RQ1: Knowledge of Trees and Climate Change*: With respect to the extent sonification and visualisation approaches can affect public climate and tree data understanding, following usage of the tool, 67% of participants believed that their knowledge and opinion on climate change and tree data increased, with the remaining 33% believing it to have remained the same. Moreover, after interacting with the data, 33% of participants reported that they could perceive tree stress and the effects of environmental conditions on the tree's growth rate after using the tool, with 67% of participants believing they might have perceived tree stress.

2) *RQ2: Customisable and Varied Data Presentation Modes*: Considering the benefits to customisable and varied presentation modes, and changes to future plans, 100% of participants reported that the system met their needs. One respondent stated that the varied presentations increases the data approachability, and that they appreciated the different types of approaches used, while another stated that they favoured the ability to create their own sonifications. 100% of participants stated that this study has inspired them to do

something new in the future, with one stating that they would like to be involved with more citizen science projects.

3) *RQ3: Sonification and Visualisation Mappings*: When asked regarding their most favoured and disliked sonification preferences, one respondent stated that they enjoyed most of the sonifications. In contrast, another respondent preferred the tree animation and musical sonifications, commenting that the drones sound 'annoying', and the Custom Audio functionality is too overwhelming.

V. DISCUSSION

This section presents a discussion on the findings, addressing each research question.

1) *RQ1: Knowledge of Trees and Climate Change*: Following usage of the tool, participants from both user studies reported that they believed their knowledge and opinion on climate change and tree data had increased, at 40% from the full study, and 67% from the evaluation study, with the remaining participants believing their knowledge remained the same. Such results suggest that, in some cases, the multimodal representations presented can benefit the perception of increased data understanding in some users, potentially as a result of the different sonification and visualisation approaches available.

Such findings align with the discoveries made by Lindborg et al. (2023), who highlighted that the different multimodal approaches used across 32 separate studies did provide data interpretation benefits to distinct groups of participants. This indicates that sonification and visualisation approaches may provide widespread benefit in the democratisation of data to the general public, particularly within a citizen science or campaign capacity. However, it must be noted that these results present subjective perceptions of increased understanding, rather than objective gains in knowledge, while the results from both small-scale studies may not generalise to wider or more diverse populations, with differing starting levels of climate change knowledge.

However, these findings contrast with participant reports regarding their ability to perceive tree stress and the influence of environmental conditions on growth. While 80% of full study participants and 67% of evaluation study participants believed they might have perceived such effects, 20% of full-study participants believed they did not. This discrepancy indicates that, although derived data presentations incorporated these calculations, they may not have effectively conveyed the interplay between variables. Alternatively, users may have lacked sufficient guidance on interpreting these relationships, as tree stress is implied by the VPD value, which could have caused confusion.

These findings imply that users may need clear guidance on interpreting complex data relationships, especially with respect to derived data. Moreover, the interface should highlight the key interplay between variables, through clear, textual descriptions or tutorials, to suitably inform users on how to interpret the data. However, it should be noted that the duration of interaction with the Derived Data presets, Personalised

Data, or Custom Audio functions, offering such insights, is not known, meaning users interacting with only the Primary Data functionality would not be presented with tree stress and growth insights.

2) *RQ2: Customisable and Varied Data Presentation Modes*: Participants within both studies believed that customisable and varied presentation modes are beneficial to their understanding of tree data and climate change, although one participant in the full study believed there was too much personalisation available, preferring refined, curated presets, with fewer customisation options. Such findings suggest that, while customisation generally enhances engagement and understanding of the data, some users may become overwhelmed when presented with multiple options. To address such concerns, it may be beneficial to provide users with guided pathways between a basic, curated presentation experience, offering few, focussed customisation controls, alongside an advanced, fully-customisable tool, as suggested by Worrall (2019). It should be noted that, given the limited sample size, and number of participants reporting such concerns, this preference may not generalise to a wider audience.

The tool shows promise in prompting changes to future plans, with 80% of full study participants and 100% of evaluation study participants stating that the study has inspired them to do something new in the future, and the remaining 20% of full study participants stating they believe it might inspire them to do something new. Such promising results indicate the potential of the tool, and varied data presentation modes, to benefit future engagement with environmental and citizen science projects, or enact changing behaviours. These findings show potential to raise public awareness and enact change within the areas of tree and climate change. However, such finding presents intentions, rather than concrete actions, thus follow-up studies would be required to determine if such plans were enacted.

3) *RQ3: Sonification and Visualisation Mappings*: Participants within both studies noted some benefit from the animation visualisations, with 80% of full study and 33% of evaluation study participants expressing use cases for such presentation, and 80% of full study participants appreciating the Custom Audio feature. Similarly, the Personalised Data function was appreciated by 60% of full user study participants. Such animation visualisation findings suggest that users identify the benefits of abstracted, simplified data presentation with real-world associations, for clear, high-level data analysis.

This aligns with the views discovered by Newell et al. (2016), who discovered similar preferences towards abstracted, real-world animated visualisations. However, the preference for the Custom Audio and Personalised Data features indicates that no singular data mapping provides the greatest engagement with the general public, with a user preference for tailoring data presentations to their own personal presentation modes, and needs. This aligns with the sonification ideas presented by both Worrall (2019) and Hermann et al. (2011), who both state the benefits of differing sonification methods, to benefit analysis of varying types of data, by individual user

groups.

These findings imply that consideration should be made to offering varied and customisable data presentation modes across modalities, benefitting diverse learning styles and increased interpretability. Moreover, the importance of mapping complex scientific data to real-world objects, to aid in user associations, is highlighted.

However, it should be noted that these findings may be caused by the preferences and background experience of the study participants, with most having experience in music, science, and pedagogy. This may increase their potential personal interest in sonification, sound customisation, from a pedagogical aspect, abstract visualisations, to benefit dissemination to non-scientists. Furthermore, no precise knowledge of the sonification and visualisation techniques used within these functions is known, thus the possibility that all participants were presenting data using the same tool settings, cannot be excluded. Moreover, the the findings from these small sample sizes limit the generalisability of these findings, particularly to users with differing backgrounds.

VI. CONCLUSIONS

This paper presents an initial exploration into the use of varied multimodal sonification and visualisation approaches to present tree and climate data, to benefit tree stress and climate change analysis, by non-experts. It examined the process of conducting a participatory design user study, to elicit and validate features and design ideas, prior to implementing a web-based sonification and visualisation tool, to investigate data presentation and mapping approaches. It was identified that such approaches can benefit public opinion and knowledge of tree and climate data, with customisable approaches providing the most benefit and greatest engagement with the general public, prompting intent to change future plans.

VII. FUTURE WORK

This preliminary study provides opportunities for extensive future work, namely involving a more comprehensive evaluation user study, recruiting greater numbers of participants from more diverse backgrounds, to evaluate the tool over a longer duration. The findings from such study are necessary to evaluate the generalisability and prolonged engagement of the sonification and visualisation approaches presented, and the data mappings used. Although an evaluation study was performed, it failed to provoke interest, thus alternative recruitment approaches must be investigated.

Moreover, implementing machine learning within the tool, to analyse the available data, and provide insights to users based on detected patterns, could offer accessibility benefits, through calculating the optimal data mappings and presentation approaches for a given dataset. Its suggestions could be particularly beneficial for non-musicians, through abstracting the sometimes overwhelming Custom Audio features, to provide a highly interpretable data presentation, while simplifying the existing process.

ETHICAL STANDARDS

This study was approved by Queen Mary University of London School of Electronic Engineering and Computer Science (EECS) Devolved School Research Ethics Committee (DSREC) (reference: QMERC20.565.DSEEC25.032). Participants provided informed consent, and full-study participants were financially compensated for their time. All participation was voluntary, with participants able to withdraw at any point without penalty. Data was anonymised, securely stored, and handled in accordance with Queen Mary University of London policies, and data protection guidelines.

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

This research is part of the Sensing the Forest project, which has received funding from the UKRI Arts and Humanities Research Council (AH/X011585/2). A special thanks to Mr Mahmoud B. Elmokadem, Dr Krishna Nama Manjunatha, and Dr Gerard Roma for their work on developing the hardware and software tree talker prototype infrastructure, Dr Georgios Xenakis for advice on tree and environmental data analysis, and Dr Anna Xambó for coordinating the Sensing the Forest project. Our sincerest appreciation goes to our participatory design user study participants, for their invaluable insights and opinions in aiding with the design and evaluation of the tool, and our feedback study participants, for providing their enlightening thoughts on the system.

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VIII. APPENDICES

A. Vapour Pressure Deficit (VPD) Formula

Below is the formula used to calculate the vapour pressure deficit (VPD).

$$VPD = \left(0.6108 \times \exp \left(\frac{17.27 \times T_{\text{air}}}{T_{\text{air}} + 237.3} \right) \right) \times \left(1 - \frac{RH}{100} \right)$$

B. Tree Mean Growth Formula

Below is the formula used to calculate Tree Mean Growth.

$$\text{Tree Mean Growth} = \text{Minimum Shrinkage Point} - \text{Maximum Expansion Point}$$

$$\text{Mean Growth} = \text{Dendrometer}_{\text{Min}} - \text{Dendrometer}_{\text{Max}}$$

C. List of Features

Below is the list of features, elicited from participatory design user study participants, and presented to users for evaluation:

General Features:

- Primary focus on sonification of long-term data, with sonification and visualisation presented together
- Both raw and derived/inference data variables should be presented
- Show base-level of average data or past data against real-time data changes
- Speed up long-term data to get tendencies and processes
- Introduce the data and trees given, and remind of the real trees (not too digital or removed from nature)
- Access to the raw data stream, for even more custom sonifications/visualisations
- Zoom into one tree, then aggregate data to the whole forest, and sonify or compare the two
- Clear nature/climate connection not just hearing the tree is dying
- Balance between scientific and creative, but focus on science
- Primary device: laptop with high-quality headphones or speakers for primarily individual listening, and background listening, with fully-fledged features

HCI Features:

- Heavy focus on usability, HCI, visual design, and accessibility
- Minimal features/controls/buttons (2-3 max per sonification/visualisation), to not be overwhelming
- Personalisation (e.g. on-screen modification/move items around/delete things/change interaction) and built-in customisable sonifications

Visualisation Features:

- Visualisation preference for charts and graphs, and detailed scientific-based graphics

Sonification Features:

- Sonification preference for semi-musical sonification (both sine waves/beep tones, and music)
- Non-tiring to listen to in the background, and not unclear or masked by the sonifier's intentions or over-artistry (should still be science-based)
- Interactive, with well-tuned sonifications, with clearly separate sonic presentation of variables, even when plotted together
- Volume mixing of individual sensor sonification streams
- Selectable time spans and averaging windows for sensor sonification streams

- Bring multiple sonification parameters together and assign them to one sensor variable
- Sonification data values could be optionally smoothed to reduce noise of sensor readings

D. Wireframes

Below are two of the key medium-fidelity wireframes evaluated by participatory design user study participants.

Fig. 4. Medium-fidelity wireframe depicting the proposed design of the data presets

Fig. 5. Medium-fidelity wireframe depicting the proposed design of the Personalised Data function